

**PERFUME ALLERGENS IN THE GCC MARKET: CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION,
HEALTH RISKS, AND REGULATORY ALIGNMENT**Pooja Thanki¹, Sudhir Sawarkar^{1*}, Kishore Machale²¹QRServes Global LLC, Dubai, UAE, ²Kairose Perfumes and Cosmetics Manufacturing LLC, UAQ, UAE.***Corresponding Author: Sudhir Sawarkar**

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ABSTRACT

This research paper examines the presence, risks, and regulation of perfume allergens in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) market. Perfumes are deeply embedded in the region's culture and daily life. Still, growing evidence shows they can cause allergic reactions—ranging from skin irritation and respiratory discomfort to, in rare cases, severe responses like anaphylaxis. To explore this issue, we employed a multidisciplinary approach that included market analysis, chemical testing using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), case reviews, and a comparison of international and regional regulations. Our findings indicate that the GCC fragrance industry is experiencing rapid expansion, driven by high consumer spending, cultural preferences, and demand for luxury and halal-certified products. Chemical analysis of popular perfumes and deodorants revealed several known allergens—such as limonene, linalool, citral, eugenol, and coumarin—present in varying concentrations across brands. Case studies from the EU, USA, and Saudi Arabia highlight the widespread nature of fragrance-related allergies. This study highlights the need for harmonized implementation across the GCC region. Although GSO 1943 is largely aligned with the European Cosmetics Regulation EC 1223/2009—adopting similar lists of prohibited ingredients, UV filters, preservatives, and labeling requirements, the actual implementation varies significantly among member countries. Each GCC nation maintains its own registration or notification system, requiring companies to navigate distinct approval processes.^[1] This fragmented approach undermines the benefits of a unified regulatory framework and poses challenges for consistent enforcement and public awareness. Testing methods such as patch testing and lab-based assays remain essential for identifying allergens and assessing product safety. Additionally, clearer labelling of allergenic ingredients and stronger public education. It also encourages the development of fragrance-free and hypoallergenic alternatives, along with continued research to improve safety and transparency in the GCC fragrance market.

KEYWORDS: Perfume Allergens, Fragrance Sensitivity, GCC Market, GC-MS Analysis, Regulatory Standards, Hypoallergenic Products.**METHODOLOGY**

This study uses a multi-disciplinary approach to explore the presence, health impact, and regulatory landscape of perfume allergens in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) market. The methodology combines market research, chemical analysis, case study reviews, and regulatory comparisons to provide a well-rounded understanding of the issue.

1. Market Analysis

To assess the scale and dynamics of the fragrance industry in the GCC, we gathered data from leading

market research platforms such as Statista, IMARC Group, Grand View Research, Mordor Intelligence, and PS Market Research. Study was focused on GCC region especially the UAE and Saudi Arabia.

1. Allergen Testing Techniques and Chemical Analysis

To evaluate allergenic potential, both clinical and laboratory testing methods are considered. Clinical Methods includes **Patch Testing** (Applying allergens to the skin under occlusion to detect delayed hypersensitivity), **Photo Patch Testing** (Like patch

testing but includes UV light exposure to identify photoallergic reactions), **Open Application Testing:** Direct application of the product to the skin without occlusion.^[2], **Laboratory Methods: In Vitro Testing**(Using cultured cells or tissues to assess allergenic potential) **and GC-MS Analysis** (Used to confirm the presence of allergenic compounds in product formulations.

Figure 1: AOC™-30i + GCMS-QP2020 NX.

We conducted chemical profiling using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), GCMS Model: GCMS-QP2020 NX, Autoinjector: AOC-30i, Column 1: SH-I-17 (30 m ×0.25 mm I.D. 0.25 μm), Column 2: SH-1 (30 m ×0.25 mm I.D. 0.25 μm) to identify and measure allergenic substances in selected perfume and deodorant samples.

GC Conditions we maintained: Injection Mode: SplitInjection, Volume: 1 μL, Injector Temp.: 280 °C, Split Ratio: 10, Carrier Gas: Helium, Carrier Gas Control: Linear velocity (40 cm/s), Column 1 (SH-I-17): Temp. Program: 80 °C (1 min)_10 °C/min_135 °C (2 min)_3 °C/min_170 °C (1 min)_10 °C/min_280 °C (2 min), Column 2 (SH-1): Temp. Program: 80 °C (4 min)_15 °C/min_105 °C (2 min)_4 °C/min_150 °C_10 °C/min_280 °C (2 min).

MS Conditions, we maintained: Ion Source Temp.: 200 °C, Interface Temp.: 280 °C, Emission Current: 20 μA, Data Acquisition Mode: SIM, Event Time: 0.3 sec.

The analysis focused on common fragrance allergens such as limonene, linalool, citral, eugenol, isoeugenol, and coumarin. Products were sourced from both local and international brands available in the GCC market, and concentrations were recorded in parts per million (ppm). A calibration curve was generated at 0.5 to 50 mg/kg by SIM measurement. The R² values of the calibration curves for each compound indicated very good linearity, with 54 out of 57 compounds showing values greater than 0.999. The remaining three compounds also demonstrated sufficient linearity for quantification, with R² values of 0.997 or higher. Notably, farnesol, benzyl salicylate, and sclareol, along with calibration curves for α-pinene, DMBC acetate, and benzyl cinnamate, exemplify the results. In terms of repeatability, the area repeatability of six consecutive

analyses at the minimum concentration (0.5 mg/kg) of the calibration curve was assessed. The area % RSD for each compound demonstrated remarkable consistency, with 97% of the compounds on the SH-I-17 column exhibiting an RSD of better than 5%. Similarly, the area RSD of 88% of the peaks on the SH-1 column also fell below this threshold. Both columns yielded excellent results, maintaining area % RSDs of less than 10% across all compounds.

3. Case Studies and Epidemiological Review

To understand the real-world impact of perfume allergens, we compiled documented allergy cases from regions including the UK, Australia, the EU, the USA, and Saudi Arabia. We also reviewed peer-reviewed studies and public health reports on fragrance sensitivity and allergic contact dermatitis. This helped contextualize the prevalence and severity of perfume-related allergies and identify vulnerable groups.

4. Regulatory Review

We compared international and regional regulations governing fragrance allergens. The review focused on: EU Cosmetics Regulation (EC 1223/2009), IFRA (International Fragrance Association) standards, GCC-specific guidelines. Key developments included the EU's expansion of its recognized allergen list from 24 to 81 substances, and an assessment of labelling requirements, banned ingredients, and safety protocols in GCC. Perfumes, also known as fragrance substances, are widely used in consumer products to enhance user experience and mask unpleasant odours from other ingredients. They are also utilized in aromatherapy. A typical perfume may contain between 10 to 300 substances selected from a pool of over 3,000 synthetic and natural fragrance materials. Studies have shown that approximately 2% of the general population is allergic to perfumes.^[3] Additionally, perfumes are a significant cause of allergic contact dermatitis from the use of cosmetics and toiletries. Other consumer products, such as perfumed laundry detergents and dishwashing liquids, have also been implicated in causing perfume allergies in contact eczema patients.

MARKET OVERVIEW OF PERFUME AND FRAGRANCE INDUSTRY

The market size of the perfume and fragrance industry exhibits significant variation across different geographical regions and market segments. As of 2025, the **global perfume market** is estimated to be valued at approximately USD 60.73 billion, with projections indicating a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.88%, potentially reaching USD 101.47 billion by 2034.^{[4][5]}

Several key factors are driving the growth of the perfume industry. These include increasing consumer disposable income, heightened demand for premium and niche fragrances, and a growing trend towards personal grooming and self-care. The Asia Pacific region is

anticipated to be the fastest-growing market, attributed to the expanding middle-class population, rising urbanization, and evolving lifestyle preferences.^{[6][7]}

The fragrance industry encompasses various segments, such as perfumes, colognes, body sprays, and other scented products, with market sizes differing for each segment.

In the **Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC)** region, the perfume market was valued at USD 3.0 billion in 2024 and is projected to reach USD 4.8 billion by 2033, growing at a CAGR of 5.09% from 2025 to 2033.^[7] The market growth in the GCC is driven by a cultural affinity for fragrances, high disposable incomes, and a luxury-oriented lifestyle.

GCC Perfume Market Drivers

The tourism sector in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) region has experienced significant growth in recent years, leading to a surge in duty-free sales. This has been a major factor boosting the perfume market in the region.^[8]

Additionally, the increasing disposable income of consumers in the GCC has enabled them to afford premium categories of fragrances and perfumes, contributing to a growing demand for high-quality products.^[9]

Furthermore, the majority of the population in the GCC follows Islamic beliefs, prompting manufacturers to produce fragrances and perfumes under halal regulations, which have positively influenced market growth.^{[10][11]}

Market Segmentation by Price

The GCC fragrance market is **dominated by premium products**, which account for approximately **81% of the market share** as of 2024. This dominance is driven by: High disposable incomes, Cultural affinity for luxury and exclusivity, Preference for artisanal and niche fragrances. The **mass market segment** caters to price-sensitive consumers and expatriates, offering affordable options like body mists and colognes. These are widely distributed through supermarkets and hypermarkets.

Market Segmentation by Gender

The GCC perfume market is segmented into: **Unisex**, **Female** and **Male**

Unisex perfumes are currently the most popular category, reflecting a shift toward **gender-neutral fragrance preferences**. This trend is especially strong among younger consumers seeking personalization and uniqueness.

Market Segmentation by Product

The GCC perfume market includes a mix of **Arabic**, **French**, and **other international styles**. It is highly fragmented, with both small artisanal producers and large manufacturers competing on quality and price.

Leading Brands: Ajmal Perfumes – Established in 1951, known for oriental scents and innovation. **Rasasi** –

Founded in 1979, offers both oriental and occidental lines, with over 165 stores across the GCC. **Arabian Oud** – The largest fragrance retailer in the Middle East, with 900 stores globally. **Abdul Samad Al Qurashi** – Established in 1852, specializes in premium oud-based fragrances. **The Fragrance Kitchen (TFK)** – A Kuwait-based brand blending traditional Middle Eastern ingredients with modern perfumery.^[8]

U.A.E. Fragrance Market Outlook

The **U.A.E. fragrance market** was valued at USD 913.7 million in 2021 and is projected to witness a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.6% from 2021 to 2030. This growth can be attributed to increased investments in advertising and marketing initiatives, particularly through digital channels, rising disposable incomes, and growing demand for custom-made, natural, and eco-friendly cosmetic products.^[12] The U.A.E. has emerged as a popular destination for investments among manufacturers and suppliers of various products. The market exhibits high growth potential due to the increasing consumer demand for personal care products.^[8] Fragrances have become essential daily products for the public. Additionally, the rise in internet penetration and the number of social media users has led key market players to promote their offerings on social media and other online platforms.^[12]

Luxury Products as Higher Revenue Generators

In 2021, luxury products held a larger revenue share, approximately 70%, in the U.A.E. fragrance market. This is due to the U.A.E.'s strong economic position, which attracts major multinational brands to launch their premium products in the country earlier than in many other markets. Additionally, around 60% of the U.A.E. population falls within the age group of 14–40, which has a significantly higher purchasing power compared to other age groups. The working population, primarily aged 18–40, acts as a powerful catalyst for the increasing demand for luxury fragrance products.^{[8][7]}

U.A.E. Fragrance Market by Product Type

Increasing Demand for Fragrance Products Among Men

There is a rising use of cosmetics among men in their daily routines, which complements market growth. Men are becoming more concerned about their grooming. After workouts, they use products containing fragrances to remove body odor. Furthermore, as urbanization increases and Western cultural influences spread beyond cities, men are opting for spicy, woody, oceanic, and citrus notes.

Perfume as the Highest Revenue Contributor

Perfumes are a crucial element of both men's and women's grooming rituals in the U.A.E., symbolizing cleanliness and excellent taste. In recent years, the U.A.E. has seen a significant increase in the number of international perfume companies establishing operations in the country. By combining traditional oriental

elements with contemporary fragrances, these companies are progressively catering to the local populace.

Surging Demand for Eco-Friendly Fragrance Products

One of the major drivers in the U.A.E. fragrance market is the increasing demand for organic and natural-ingredient-based products. Common ingredients in such fragrances include sandalwood, geranium bourbon, and patchouli. However, the industry relies on synthetic components, with synthetic fragrances accounting for 60–65% of the total market. In contrast, 30–35% of the market comprises fragrances made from natural ingredients. The rising consumer awareness related to ingredients used in fragrances, driven by a focus on personal health and hygiene and changing lifestyles, supports the demand for organic fragrances.

Globally, including in the U.A.E., people are becoming increasingly aware of the importance of a healthy lifestyle. As a result, fitness has become a prime focus for millions, leading to a significant rise in the number of gym-goers. According to the Dubai World Trade Centre, the U.A.E. has eight hundred fitness clubs with 523,000 members. Health clubs and gyms offering personal training and advanced exercise equipment are projected to promote market growth, as consumers in the U.A.E. are willing to spend more on fragrances to mask unpleasant odours after intense workouts.

PERFUME ALLERGIES CASES

Perfume allergies are common and can manifest through various symptoms such as skin irritation, itching, rash, headache, sneezing, and coughing. In severe cases, they can lead to asthma attacks or anaphylaxis. Below are some recent examples of perfume allergy cases reported.

United Kingdom, 2018: A woman reported a severe allergic reaction to a perfume sample received by mail. Symptoms included breathing difficulties, hives, and facial swelling.^[13] **Australia, 2016:** A woman experienced an allergic reaction to a popular celebrity-endorsed perfume brand, resulting in red, swollen, and itchy skin.^[14] **Global Study 2014:** A study published in the *Journal of Environmental Health Perspectives* found that fragrance exposure can trigger asthma symptoms in some individuals. The study analysed data from over 38,000 adults and found a correlation between frequent perfume or cologne use and reported asthma symptoms.^[15] **European Union, 2023:** The European Union expanded the list of recognized allergenic substances in fragrances to eighty-one, up from twenty-four. This update followed the opinion issued by the European Scientific Committee for Consumer Safety (SCCS) in 2012.^[16] **California, 2024:** The California Department of Public Health reported that approximately one-third of people experience negative health effects from using or being around fragranced products. Fragrance allergens can cause skin allergies, respiratory issues, and other health problems.^[3]

It is important to note that diagnosing fragrance allergies can be challenging due to the presence of various chemicals in perfumes, and reactions can vary significantly among individuals. If a perfume allergy is suspected, consulting a healthcare professional for proper diagnosis and treatment is recommended.

NEWS AND UPDATES ON ALLERGENS RESTRICTION IN GCC

On August 23, 2021, the Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) issued an official circular banning the use of Lylal (Hydroxyisohexyl 3-Cyclohexene Carboxaldehyde) in cosmetic products. The decision was based on scientific evidence indicating that Lylal is a skin sensitizer and may cause allergic reactions, making it unsafe for consumer use. The Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) has officially added Lilial (Butylphenyl Methylpropional) to its prohibited substances list for cosmetic products. This decision is based on scientific findings that Lilial poses reproductive toxicity risks and can cause skin sensitization, aligning with international safety standards.^[17] On 19 December 2022, Dubai Municipality issued a public statement addressing concerns about products containing Lilial (Butylphenyl Methylpropional). The authority reassured consumers that all locally manufactured and imported personal care products undergo rigorous inspection and testing to meet health and safety standards and urged the public to report any adverse effects via the Montaji system or call centre.^[18] On 23 November 2022, the Kuwaiti Union of Consumer Cooperative Societies, under ministerial directives, announced a ban on cosmetics containing Lilial (Butylphenyl Methylpropional) due to its classification as a carcinogen by the European Chemicals Agency. The decision included a nationwide withdrawal of affected products and inspection campaigns to ensure compliance and protect consumer health.^[19] On 3 December 2023, the Consumer Protection Authority (CPA) of Oman seized 780 cosmetic products falsely labelled as free from Lilial (Butylphenyl Methylpropional), despite containing the banned substance. This action was taken under Resolution No. 845/2022, which prohibits the distribution of Lilial-containing products, and in accordance with Article 7 of the Consumer Protection Law, ensuring consumer safety and preventing deceptive practices.^[20] As of now, Qatar and Bahrain have not issued publicly available government circulars specifically banning Lilial or Lylal in cosmetic products. However, both countries adhere to GSO 1943 and GSO 2528 standards, which are harmonized with EU safety regulations. These standards indirectly restrict the use of hazardous fragrance allergens, promoting safer formulations and consumer protection. On 7 October 2020, the Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) issued a warning against five perfumes found to contain methanol levels exceeding safety limits under SFDA/CO/GSO 1943:2016. Methanol is a highly toxic substance that can cause neurological symptoms, respiratory irritation, and skin and eye damage. The

SFDA advised consumers to avoid these products and initiated a recall in cooperation with relevant authorities.^[21] On 3 March 2024, the Consumer Protection Authority (CPA) of Oman issued Decision No. 579/2024, banning the use of Methyl-N-Methylantranilate (MNM) in cosmetics and personal care products above specified concentrations. Violations of this regulation may result in fines of up to OMR 2,000, reinforcing the country's commitment to consumer health and product safety.^[22] On 3 July 2023, the Ministry of Commerce and Industry (MOCI) of Qatar conducted an inspection campaign targeting an unlicensed factory in South Muaither. Authorities seized concentrated perfume solutions of unknown origin used in counterfeit products, reinforcing Qatar's commitment to consumer safety and the enforcement of regulations against unregulated allergens and unsafe manufacturing practices.^[23]

PERFUME AND FRAGRANCE ALLERGENS AS PUBLIC HEALTH CONCERN

As of 2025, perfume and fragrance allergies continue to be a significant public health concern globally. Recent studies highlight the prevalence and impact of perfume allergies.

Global Prevalence: Approximately 1.9% of the general population in five European countries (Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, and Sweden) have a fragrance contact allergy, as determined by patch testing.^[24]

Fragrance Sensitivity in the U.S.: About 30.5% of the American population reports irritation from scented products used by others, and 19% experience adverse health effects from air fresheners.^[25]

Fragrance Sensitivity in Saudi Arabia: A study in the Eastern Province of Saudi Arabia found that 50.6% of participants reported at least one adverse reaction from cosmetic products, including perfumes.^[26]

Fragrance Sensitivity and Asthma: Individuals with asthma are more susceptible to fragrance allergies, with exposure potentially exacerbating their symptoms.^[27]

These statistics underscore the growing need for fragrance-free alternatives, transparent labelling, and inclusive public policies to address the health impacts of perfume allergens.^[15]

PERFUME AND FRAGRANCE ALLERGIES AWARENESS DRIVES IN GCC

United Arab Emirates – Dubai Municipality: Dubai Municipality actively promotes consumer safety through: Participation in Beauty World Middle East 2024, showcasing its advanced laboratory testing systems for cosmetics and perfumes. Use of over 5,000 testing techniques, including allergen screening and banned substance detection. Public education on perfume safety and allergen risks via exhibitions and media.^[28]

Saudi Arabia – SFDA: The Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) provides: Public guidelines on cosmetic classification and allergen disclosure. Consumer education on how product claims (e.g., aromatherapy)

may reclassify cosmetics as drugs. Online access to safety requirements and labelling regulations.^[29] **Oman – Consumer Protection Authority (CPA):** CPA Oman runs: The “Your Awareness is a Responsibility” forum, educating consumers on risks of unsafe products including cosmetics. A bilingual e-portal offering multimedia content, complaint handling, and awareness publications. Campaigns targeting fragrance safety and counterfeit product risks.^[30]

Qatar – Ministry of Commerce and Industry: Qatar's MOCI launched: The “Know Your Right as a Consumer” radio program, educating the public on consumer rights, counterfeit detection, and safe product use. Weekly broadcasts with expert interviews and public engagement.^[31] **Kuwait – Environment Public Authority:** Kuwait's EPA contributes through: **Chemical Safety Department initiatives**, including public lectures and media campaigns on safe chemical handling in perfumes. Participation in **national awareness campaigns** and school programs.^[32]

Common Allergens in GCC Perfumes: Perfumes in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) market may contain various allergens, including but not limited to.

Fragrance Ingredients: Perfumes contain a variety of fragrance ingredients that can cause allergic reactions in some individuals. Common allergens include limonene, linalool, eugenol, and coumarin.

Essential Oils (e.g., Lavender Oil): Essential oils, including lavender, are widely used in perfumes and aromatherapy products. Despite being natural, they can cause allergic contact dermatitis or respiratory issues. The FDA notes that essential oils marketed for therapeutic use (e.g., relaxation, pain relief) may be regulated as drugs due to their potential health effects. The agency warns that natural origin does not guarantee safety. **1. Lavender oil** contains linalool and linalyl acetate, which are known allergens. These compounds can oxidize and become more allergenic over time. **2. Balsam of Peru** is a natural resin used for its sweet, spicy scent in perfumes and flavorings. It is a well-known allergen. The FDA includes Balsam of Peru in its list of fragrance allergens that may cause allergic contact dermatitis. It contains cinnamic acid, benzyl benzoate, and vanillin—compounds known to trigger reactions in sensitive individuals. **3. Musk Compounds,** Synthetic musks (e.g., musk ketone, musk xylene) are used as fixatives in perfumes but have been associated with allergic reactions and environmental concerns. The FDA acknowledges that some fragrance ingredients, including musk, may cause sensitivities or allergic reactions in certain individuals. Musk compounds are also under scrutiny for potential bioaccumulation and endocrine disruption, prompting regulatory reviews in the EU.

It is important to note that fragrance ingredients are not always required to be listed on perfume labels, making it difficult to determine which allergens may be present in a particular perfume. Individuals with a history of allergic reactions to perfumes or fragrance ingredients are advised to perform a patch test before using any new perfume.^{[33], [34]}

COMMON ALLERGENS IN PERFUMES

Perfumes may contain various allergens, including but not limited to: Limonene, Linalool, Eugenol, Coumarin, Alpha-isomethyl ionone, Geraniol, Citronellol, Hydroxyisohexyl 3-cyclohexene carboxaldehyde (HICC), Benzyl alcohol, Benzyl benzoate, Farnesol, Isoeugenol, Citral, Cinnamaldehyde, Cinnamyl alcohol, Anise alcohol, Amyl cinnamal, Evernia prunastri extract (oakmoss extract), Evernia furfuracea extract (treemoss extract), Hexyl cinnamaldehyde, Hydroxycitronellal, Methyl 2-octynoate, Methyl eugenol, Oakmoss absolute, Tree moss extract New Additions: Butylphenyl methylpropional (Lilial), Hydroxycitronellal, Benzyl salicylate.

Allergens in Natural Fragrances, Natural essential oils, commonly used in perfumes, can contain allergens. These highly concentrated plant extracts include volatile organic compounds (VOCs) that may cause allergic reactions in some individuals. Common allergenic essential oils include: Lavender oil, Tea tree oil, Peppermint oil, Eucalyptus oil, Geranium oil, Ylang Ylang oil, Bergamot oil, Patchouli oil, Chamomile oil, Citrus oils (such as orange, lemon, and grapefruit). The specific allergens in essential oils can vary based on the plant type, extraction method, and other factors. For example, lavender oil contains linalool and linalyl acetate, which are known allergens for some people. It is crucial to use essential oils with caution, especially for individuals with a history of allergies or sensitive skin. A patch test is recommended before using any new essential oil. Additionally, essential oils should always be diluted and never applied directly to the skin.

Allergen Testing in Cosmetics

Cosmetic allergen testing methods are essential for identifying potential allergens in cosmetics and personal care products. The commonly used methods include.

Patch Testing: This is the gold standard for cosmetic allergen testing. A small amount of the cosmetic product is applied to the skin (usually the back) and covered with a patch for 48 hours. The patch is then removed, and the skin is examined for any signs of irritation or allergic reaction. This method can identify both immediate and delayed allergic reactions.^[2]

Open Application Testing: This method involves applying the cosmetic product to a small area of skin and leaving it uncovered for a period. It is used to evaluate for immediate reactions.

Photo patch Testing: Like patch testing, but the skin is also exposed to light (usually UV light) during the

testing period. This method is used to evaluate for photoallergic reactions, which are allergic reactions triggered by exposure to light.

In Vitro Testing: This involves evaluating the cosmetic product on cells or tissues in a laboratory setting. It can identify potential allergens before the product is marketed, but it is not as accurate as patch testing. It is important to note that cosmetic allergen testing can be complex and may require specialized expertise. Individuals suspecting an allergy to a cosmetic product should consult with a dermatologist or allergist who can help identify the allergen and recommend appropriate treatment.

Chemical Testing of Fragrance Allergens: GC-MS (Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry) is a commonly used method for the detection and identification of fragrance allergens in cosmetic products. The process involves.

Gas Chromatography: The cosmetic sample is injected into a gas chromatograph, which separates the different components of the sample based on their chemical properties. This separation occurs due to the interaction of the sample components with a stationary phase and a moving gas phase.

Mass Spectrometry: The separated components then enter a mass spectrometer, which ionizes the molecules and separates them based on their mass-to-charge ratio. The mass spectrometer generates a mass spectrum, which is a unique fingerprint for each compound in the sample.

Identification: The mass spectrum is compared to a database of known fragrance allergens. If a match is found, the identity of the allergen can be confirmed.

GC-MS is an overly sensitive and specific method for detecting fragrance allergens and can detect allergens at extremely low concentrations. However, it is not a substitute for clinical testing such as patch testing, which remains the gold standard for diagnosing allergic reactions to cosmetics. GC-MS is also an expensive and time-consuming method, requiring specialized equipment and expertise to perform.

STRUCTURE OF ALLERGENS IN PERFUME

Perfume allergens are typically **small, volatile organic compounds (VOCs)** that easily evaporate and become airborne, making them readily inhaled or absorbed through the skin. These compounds are primarily used in **fragrance formulations** to impart distinctive scents to perfumes and other scented products.

Key Chemical Classes of Perfume Allergens

Perfume allergens span a variety of chemical structures, each contributing to scent and potential allergenicity.

Terpenes: Naturally occurring in essential oils, terpenes are common fragrance ingredients. Examples include: *Limonene*, *Linalool*, *Geraniol*, **Aldehydes:** Synthetic compounds used to create floral, fruity, or woody notes. Examples include: *Citral*, *Cinnamaldehyde*, *Benzaldehyde*, **Musk Compounds:** Used as fixatives to prolong scent longevity. Examples include: *Musk ambrette*, *Musk xylene*, *Musk ketone*, **Phenols:** Contribute spicy, smoky, or woody tones. Examples include: *Eugenol*, *Isoeugenol*, *Hydroxyisohexyl 3-cyclohexene carboxaldehyde*.

Allergic Reactions and Immune Sensitivity

In sensitive individuals, perfume allergens can trigger an **immune response**, where the body produces antibodies that recognize specific chemical structures. The **reactivity and molecular size** of these compounds influence their allergenic potential: **Smaller, more reactive molecules** tend to be more potent allergens. **Higher concentrations** of allergens in products increase the risk and severity of reactions.

Regulated Allergens ²			
1. Amyl Cinnamaldehyde CAS: 122-40-7 (C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O) 			
5. Eugenol CAS: 97-54-0 (C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂) 			
9. Benzyl salicylate CAS: 118-58-1 (C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂) 			
13. Lyral CAS: 31906-04-4 (C ₁₃ H ₂₂ O ₂) 			
17. Lilial CAS: 80-54-6 (C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O) 			
21. Hexyl cinnamaldehyde CAS: 101-86-0 (C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O) 			
Additional compounds considered			
25. Atranol CAS: 526-37-4 (C ₈ H ₈ O ₂) 			
28. Methyl eugenol CAS: 93-15-2 (C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂) 			

Figure 1: Structure of Allergens regulated under Cosmetic Regulations^[35]

INTERNATIONAL REGULATIONS

Several international regulations govern the use of allergens in cosmetics. Here are some of the most significant ones.

EU Cosmetics Regulation: The EU Cosmetics Regulation (Regulation EC 1223/2009) mandates the labelling of twenty-six fragrance allergens if they are present above certain limits. Manufacturers must also provide safety assessments for their products before marketing them in the EU.^[36]

International Fragrance Association (IFRA): IFRA sets voluntary guidelines for the use of fragrance materials in cosmetics and other consumer products. These guidelines are based on safety assessments and are updated regularly.^[34]

US FDA: The US FDA regulates cosmetics under the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act. While there are no specific regulations on fragrance allergens, the FDA requires that cosmetic manufacturers ensure their products are safe for use and properly labeled.^[37] However, a 2025 regulatory freeze may delay implementation of new allergen labelling policies.^[38]

Health Canada: Health Canada regulates cosmetics under the Food and Drugs Act and the Cosmetic Regulations. Manufacturers must disclose all ingredients on the product label, including fragrance ingredients.^[39]

ASEAN Cosmetics Directive: This directive sets guidelines for the use of fragrance materials in cosmetics in the ASEAN region. It requires that fragrance allergens be listed on the product label if present above certain limits.^[40]

These regulations aim to protect consumers from potential risks associated with exposure to allergens in cosmetics. Manufacturers are required to conduct safety assessments and properly label their products, helping consumers make informed decisions.

GCC Regulations: The GCC (Gulf Cooperation Council) countries have regulations to ensure the safety of cosmetics, including regulations on allergens. Key regulations include.

GCC Standardization Organization (GSO): The GSO standard on cosmetic products (GSO 1943/2016) includes requirements for labelling and safety assessment. Cosmetic products must be safe for human use, and ingredients must be disclosed on the label.^[41]

Dubai Municipality: Responsible for regulating cosmetic products in Dubai, the municipality maintains a list of banned and restricted ingredients, including some fragrance allergens.^[42]

Qatar General Organization for Standards and Metrology (QGOSM): QGOSM regulates cosmetic

products in Qatar, with standards for safety assessment and labelling.

These regulations aim to protect consumers from potential risks associated with allergens in cosmetics. Manufacturers must ensure their products are safe and properly labelled, aiding consumers in making informed choices.

KSA Regulations: The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) has regulations governing the use of allergens in cosmetics: **Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA):** The SFDA regulates cosmetics in Saudi Arabia, requiring all cosmetic products to be safe for use and comply with SFDA guidelines.^[43] **Labelling Requirements:** Cosmetic products must be labelled in Arabic and English, listing all ingredients, including known allergens, in descending order of concentration. **Restrictions on Allergens:** The SFDA restricts the use of certain allergens in cosmetic products. For example, formaldehyde and formaldehyde-releasing preservatives are limited to 0.2%. **Product Registration:** All cosmetic products must be registered with the SFDA before sale in Saudi Arabia. Manufacturers must provide safety assessments and demonstrate compliance with regulations.

In summary, SFDA regulations in KSA require cosmetic products to be safe, properly labelled, and compliant with SFDA guidelines. Manufacturers must register their products and provide safety assessments, ensuring allergens are properly labelled and their concentrations restricted.^[43]

INTERNATIONAL PROHIBITIONS AND RESTRICTIONS

Canada: Canada has implemented phased compliance for mandatory labeling of fragrance allergens under the Cosmetic Regulations of the Food and Drugs Act: By April 2026: Disclosure of 24 allergens (e.g., Linalool, Limonene, Citral). By August 2026: Disclosure of 81 allergens, including Isoeugenol, Coumarin, Benzyl alcohol, Oak moss, and Tree moss.

Thresholds: 0.01% for rinse-off products and 0.001% for leave-on products.^[44]

European Union: The EU has banned several allergens and requires labelling of 80+ fragrance allergens under Regulation (EU) 2023/1545, amending Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009. Banned substances: Atranol and Chloroatranol (components of Oak moss and Tree moss), HICC (Lyril).

Mandatory labelling for allergens such as: Citronellol, Isoeugenol, Limonene, Benzyl alcohol, Coumarin, Geraniol

Thresholds: 0.001% for leave-on products And 0.01% for rinse-off products.^[16]

South Korea: In 2021, South Korea's Ministry of Food and Drug Safety (MFDS) banned MIT and MCIT in cosmetics due to sensitisation risks. Additional prohibited substances include: Perfluorinated compounds (e.g., Perfluorononanoic acid), 1,2,4-Trihydroxybenzene Persistent pollutants under the Persistent Organic Pollutants Control Act.^[45]

United States: The FDA has not banned specific cosmetic allergens but actively monitors and recalls products causing allergic reactions. Common allergens include: Fragrances (e.g., Linalool, Limonene), Preservatives like Formaldehyde-releasing agents. The FDA enforces recalls and issues safety alerts based on adverse reaction reports. An elaborated, 15-line version of your paragraph, suitable for a formal scientific journal article.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

A comprehensive investigation into the allergenic constituents of several commercial perfume products was undertaken to elucidate their ingredient profiles. The primary analytical technique employed for this profiling was Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), selected for its high resolution and sensitivity in identifying volatile and semi-volatile compounds within

complex matrices. To ensure the relevance of our findings, a diverse range of fragrance products was procured directly from commercial retail markets. Immediately upon acquisition, all samples were subjected to a rigorous blinding protocol to ensure analytical impartiality and maintain commercial confidentiality.

Each product was assigned a unique laboratory code, designated sequentially as MS-01, MS-02, and so on, and was subsequently stored under controlled laboratory conditions to preserve its chemical integrity prior to analysis. The primary objective of the GC-MS analysis was the qualitative and semi-quantitative determination of known fragrance allergens. For the purpose of clear presentation and to facilitate a direct comparison between the different formulations, the detailed findings are systematically summarized in the subsequent tabulated form (Table [Insert Table Number]). This table delineates the specific allergens identified within each market sample. It is important to note that all raw instrumental data, including the total ion chromatograms and the corresponding mass spectral data for each identified peak, have been securely archived and are retained at the laboratory for verification and future reference.

Allergen: Limonene

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0.003113891
MS-03	0.000125978	MS-13	0.000156906
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000486579	MS-15	0
MS-06	0	MS-16	0.002672527
MS-07	0	MS-17	0.001930855
MS-08	0.000160716	MS-18	0.000241584
MS-09	0	MS-19	0
MS-10	0	MS-20	0.000255552

Allergen: Benzyl Alcohol

Perfume	PPM	Perfume	PPM
MS-01	0	MS-11	0
MS-02	0.00001	MS-12	0
MS-03	0.000069493	MS-13	0.001011035
MS-04	0	MS-14	0.000209583
MS-05	0.017462393	MS-15	0
MS-06	0	MS-16	0
MS-07	0	MS-17	0
MS-08	0.001344303	MS-18	0.006553708
MS-09	0	MS-19	0
MS-10	0	MS-20	0.000534764

Allergen: Geraniol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0	MS-11	0
MS-02	0.001287	MS-12	0.06712
MS-03	0.004179	MS-13	0.00025237
MS-04	0	MS-14	0.00034802
MS-05	1.324016	MS-15	0
MS-06	0	MS-16	0.309207
MS-07	0	MS-17	0.344766
MS-08	0	MS-18	0
MS-09	0	MS-19	0.000767
MS-10	0	MS-20	0.006163

Allergen: Citral

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	2.6024	MS-11	0
MS-02	2.360257	MS-12	4.396235
MS-03	6.492274	MS-13	7.1391103
MS-04	0	MS-14	170.8743
MS-05	2.84275	MS-15	0
MS-06	0	MS-16	2.117687
MS-07	0	MS-17	2.997907
MS-08	2.977743	MS-18	1.905326
MS-09	0	MS-19	7.7851
MS-10	0	MS-20	1.67659

Allergen: Eugenol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.0626	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.0008159
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0	MS-15	0.001293
MS-06	0	MS-16	0.085421
MS-07	0.004844	MS-17	0.040731
MS-08	0.00012	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.000157	MS-19	0.023938
MS-10	0.000779	MS-20	0

Allergen: Anisyl Alcohol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.3850	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.0019875
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000816	MS-15	0.000307
MS-06	0.000982	MS-16	0.008433
MS-07	0.023039	MS-17	0.006099
MS-08	0.372076	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.000852	MS-19	0.001031
MS-10	0.000179	MS-20	0

Allergen: Iso Eugenol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	2.6237	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	7.245674
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.01273	MS-15	2.80595
MS-06	0.004999	MS-16	8.263301
MS-07	1.08815	MS-17	4.517038
MS-08	0.372076	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.687696	MS-19	1.317623
MS-10	3.066844	MS-20	0

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	1.5397	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.068234008
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0	MS-15	0.048619725
MS-06	0.00016838	MS-16	1.846220647
MS-07	0.009856597	MS-17	0.737094836
MS-08	0.000445637	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.000005765	MS-19	0.009247113
MS-10	0	MS-20	0

Allergen: Farnesol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	3.8153	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.0031727
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000348	MS-15	0.007176
MS-06	0.000478	MS-16	3.493651
MS-07	0.081496	MS-17	16.84388
MS-08	0.004869	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.00077	MS-19	4.176686
MS-10	0.092094	MS-20	0

Allergen: Amyl Cinnamal

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	3.6258	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.785856732
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000700641	MS-15	0.021672169
MS-06	0.00090959	MS-16	0.757595748
MS-07	0.098208691	MS-17	0.320594692
MS-08	0.011078782	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.00084139	MS-19	0.017695802
MS-10	0.015053233	MS-20	0

Allergen: Amyl Cinnamal Alcohol

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.2867	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.229520529
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000764209	MS-15	0.021672169
MS-06	0.000734272	MS-16	0.210352337
MS-07	0.488535977	MS-17	0.041051996
MS-08	0.015139387	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.002663906	MS-19	0.136572801
MS-10	0	MS-20	0

Allergen: Hexyl Cinnamal

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.0058	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.000609229
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000844817	MS-15	0.650836498
MS-06	0.001121739	MS-16	1.906539489
MS-07	0.000212408	MS-17	0.862276214
MS-08	0.000272629	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.001719104	MS-19	0.126907617
MS-10	0.001458509	MS-20	0

Allergen: Benzyl Salicylate

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.0020	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.054149
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.000069	MS-15	0.098078
MS-06	0.000064	MS-16	1.820688
MS-07	0.002588	MS-17	0.810818
MS-08	0.000131	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.000758	MS-19	0.353818
MS-10	0.004583	MS-20	0

Allergen: Benzyl Benzoate

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	2.3654	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	3.278980404
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0.0011026	MS-15	0.059699
MS-06	0.0013431	MS-16	2.406947
MS-07	0.0045154	MS-17	1.1448352
MS-08	0.0001869	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.0030802	MS-19	0.7183333
MS-10	0	MS-20	0

Allergen: Benzyl Cinnamate

Perfumes	PPM	Perfumes	PPM
MS-01	0.0209	MS-11	0
MS-02	0	MS-12	0
MS-03	0	MS-13	0.001294565
MS-04	0	MS-14	0
MS-05	0	MS-15	0
MS-06	0	MS-16	0.00205915
MS-07	0	MS-17	0.00041658
MS-08	0	MS-18	0
MS-09	0.00016041	MS-19	0.00029852
MS-10	0.00020522	MS-20	0

RESULTS

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was conducted on a range of perfume and deodorant samples available in the GCC market. The study focused on detecting known fragrance allergens and quantifying their concentrations in parts per million (PPM). Key findings include.

Citral was found in MS-14 at 170.87 PPM, the highest concentration among all samples. – But no allergens & ingredients are mentioned in the label. Farnesol was detected in MS-17 at 16.84 PPM, significantly above typical safety thresholds. Isoeugenol appeared in MS-16 at 8.26 PPM, and in MS-13 at 7.24 PPM. Geraniol was present in MS-05 at 1.32 PPM, and in MS-17 at 0.34 PPM. Benzyl Alcohol was found in MS-05 at 0.017 PPM, and in MS-18 at 0.0065 PPM. Limonene was detected in MS-12 at 0.0031 PPM, and in MS-16 at 0.0026 PPM. Anisyl Alcohol, Amyl Cinnamal, Hexyl Cinnamal, and Benzyl Salicylate were also found in multiple samples, with concentrations ranging from 0.0002 to 3.62 PPM.

These results indicate that several allergens are present in commonly used fragrances, with some exceeding internationally recognized safety thresholds. During our field visit (GCC), it was observed that a few brands complied with the GSO 1943 standard, and a few brands do not declare allergens and ingredients.

DISCUSSION

The GC-MS analysis confirms the widespread presence of fragrance allergens in perfumes marketed in the GCC region. Notably, substances such as **Citral, Isoeugenol, Farnesol, and Geraniol** were found in concentrations that may pose health risks, especially to individuals with fragrance sensitivities or allergic predispositions.

According to **EU Regulation 2023/1545**, allergens must be labeled if present above **0.001% (10 PPM)** in leave-on products and **0.01% (100 PPM)** in rinse-off products. Several samples in this study exceeded these thresholds, suggesting potential non-compliance with international safety standards.

The findings underscore the need for: **Stricter enforcement of allergen labeling** in the GCC. **Harmonization of regional regulations** with global frameworks like the EU Cosmetics Regulation and IFRA standards. **Consumer education** on allergen risks and safe usage practices. **Encouragement of hypoallergenic formulations** and fragrance-free alternatives. This study provides a compelling case for regulatory reform and industry accountability to safeguard public health in the GCC fragrance market.

Author also understand the batchwise variations in composition of material hence manufacture can bring control over these allergens by stricter quality control.

CONCLUSION

Perfume allergens present a growing public health concern in the GCC region, where fragrance use is culturally significant and widespread. This study revealed that many commonly available perfumes contain known allergens such as **Citral, Isoeugenol, Farnesol, and Geraniol**, some in concentrations exceeding internationally accepted safety thresholds. Despite global regulatory advancements—particularly in the EU—GCC countries exhibit fragmented enforcement and inconsistent labeling practices.

The findings underscore the need for harmonized regulations, transparent ingredient disclosure, and increased public awareness. Without these measures, consumers remain vulnerable to allergic reactions, especially those with pre-existing sensitivities. The study advocates for initiative-taking steps by both industry and regulators to ensure safer fragrance formulations and informed consumer choices.

RECOMMENDATIONS

For Brand Owners and Manufacturers

Adopt Transparent Labelling Practices - Clearly disclose all fragrance ingredients, especially known allergens, using INCI names and multilingual formats to ensure consumer understanding. **Formulate Safer Products** - Reformulate products to exclude high-risk allergens such as Liliol, Lyril, and Methanol. Consider using hypoallergenic or IFRA-compliant fragrance materials. **Invest in Allergen Testing** - Implement routine GC-MS and patch testing during product development to identify and mitigate allergenic risks. **Align with Global Standards** - Follow EU SCCS, IFRA, and GSO guidelines to ensure regulatory compliance and international market readiness. **Educate Retailers and Distributors** - Provide training and resources to help retail partners understand allergen risks and communicate them effectively to consumers.

For Regulatory Authorities **Enforce Harmonized Standards Across GCC** - Collaborate to create unified fragrance safety regulations and recall protocols. **Expand Ingredient Databases** - Maintain and update public databases of banned and restricted substances, accessible to manufacturers and consumers. **Support Research and Innovation** - Fund studies on emerging allergens and promote safer alternatives through grants and partnerships.

For Consumers : Read Labels Carefully - Look for allergen disclosures and avoid products with known sensitizers if you have a history of allergies. **Perform Patch Tests** - Before using a new fragrance product, apply a small amount to your skin and monitor for reactions over 24–48 hours. **Report Adverse Reactions** - Use platforms like **Montaji (UAE)** or **SFDA portals (Saudi Arabia)** to report any allergic responses to cosmetic products. **Choose Hypoallergenic or**

Fragrance-Free Options - opt for products labelled as hypoallergenic or free from common allergens, especially if you have sensitive skin or respiratory conditions. **Stay Informed** - Follow updates from local health authorities and consumer protection agencies regarding banned substances and product recalls.

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